

Chromium Powder in Organic Synthesis.

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In a recent paper by Roy and Dutt (this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 108) aluminium powder has been successfully employed in a number of organic syntheses of the types already elaborated by Frankland, Ullmann, Fittig, Reformatski, Wislicenus and others, using metals like sodium, copper, silver, zinc and mercury. From the results of that investigation it was thought that the metal chromium (which has become very cheap now-a-days on account of its manufacture by the 'thermite' process, and) which has similar properties to aluminium both physical and chemical, would also lend itself to organic syntheses. This would be interesting in view of the fact that the metal chromium has not, up to this time, been employed in organic reactions. These expectations have been partially realised and the following results have been arrived at.

1. Metallic chromium behaves in a similar manner to aluminium in most of the reactions that have been studied, but the vigour of the reaction is somewhat less and consequently the yields of the products are somewhat lower.

2. Unlike aluminium, chromium does not react with organic bromine and iodine compounds.

3. The successful results with chromium have been obtained with organic chlorine compounds in which the chlorine atoms are rather loosely attached to the molecule.

4. Chromium when freshly powdered from lump is found to be more reactive than the powder which has stood for some time.

5. The activity of the powder which has stood for some time can be renovated to a certain extent by heating it to red-heat in a current of pure dry hydrogen.

6. Chromium cannot be used in Reformatski's and Gattermann's syntheses, nor as a neutral reducing agent.

In all the cases referred to in this paper chromium was powdered by human agency, and naturally the powder was not so fine as in the case of other metals. Hence probably if the powder had been more fine, the yields in the cases of successful reactions would have been greatly increased.

The following two tables summarise successful and unsuccessful attempts using metallic chromium in various types of organic syntheses.

TABLE I.

Successful Attempts.

Type of reaction.	Reacting materials.	Product.	Yield (%).
Zincke's	Benzylchloride and benzene	Diphenylmethane	42
Friedel-Crafts'	Benzalchloride ,, ,,	Triphenylmethane	19.5
.. ..	Benzotrichloride ,, ,,	Triphenylchloromethane	17
.. ..	Benzoylchloride ,, ,,	Benzophenone	9
.. ,, ..	Triphenylcarbinol	28
.. ..	Benzoylchloride and benzoic acid	Benzoylbenzoic acid	22
.. ..	Acetylchloride and benzene	Acetophenone	11
Ullmann's	Ethyl chloracetate and ethyl acetate	Ethyl succinate	10
.. ..	Chloroacetic acid and acetic acid	Succinic acid	6
.. ..	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid and aniline	Phenylanthranilic acid	87
.. ..	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid and ammonia	Anthranilic acid	85

TABLE II.
Unsuccessful Attempts.

Types of reaction.	Reacting materials.	Expected product.
Ullmann's	Bromobenzene	Diphenyl
,,	Iodobenzene	,,
Friedel-Crafts'	Bromobenzene and benzene	,,
,,	Iodobenzene and ,,	,,
Ullmann's	Bromobenzene and phenol	Diphenylether
,,	Chlorobenzene ,, ,,	,,
,,	Bromobenzene and aniline	Diphenylamine
,,	Carbon tetrachloride	Hexachlorethane
Reformatski's	Acetophenone and ethyl bromacetate	Phenylmethyl-β-hydroxy ethylpropionate
Friedel-Crafts'	Chloroform and benzene	Triphenylmethane
,, ,,	Carbon tetrachloride and benzene	Triphenylchloromethane
Ullmann's	Dinitrochlorobenzene	Tetranitrodiphenyl
Wislicenus'	β-Iodopropionic acid	Adipic acid
,,	Chloroacetic acid	Succinic acid
Goske's	Thiodiphenylamine .	Carbazole
Neutral reduction	Nitrobenzene and ammonium chloride	Phenylhydroxylamine

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diphenylmethane from Benzylchloride and Benzene.

A mixture of benzene (30 g.), benzyl chloride (15 g.) and freshly powdered chromium (5 g.) was heated on the water-bath under reflux for about three hours, till the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased. The reaction product was treated with a very dilute solution of caustic soda and then extracted with ether. The ether and the excess of benzene were then distilled off and the residual oil fractionated under diminished pressure. The diphenylmethane distilled off as a pale yellow liquid with a pronounced orange smell at $101^{\circ}/40$ mm.

Triphenylmethane from Chloroform and Benzene.

This was prepared in a similar manner to the method already described by Roy and Dutt (*loc. cit.*) in the case of aluminium powder.

Triphenylchloromethane from Benzotrichloride and Benzene.

A mixture of benzotrichloride (9.7 g.), benzene (22 g.) and freshly powdered chromium (5 g.) was heated on the water-bath under reflux for about five hours. The mixture was then poured into a few c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and shaken well. The benzene layer was then separated, washed with water, dried and then distilled, at first under ordinary pressure and then under reduced pressure. The triphenylchloromethane distilled over as a pale yellow oil which solidified in the receiver as pale yellow needles melting at 106° . It gave triphenylcarbinol on boiling with water.

Triphenylcarbinol from Benzoylchloride and Benzene.

This was prepared from benzoylchloride, benzene and chromium powder in a manner similar to the above. The substance crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow needles melting at 160° . The acetyl derivative which was prepared melted at 97° .

Benzophenone from Benzoylchloride and Benzene.

This was prepared in a similar manner to the above from the same ingredients, with the only difference that the theoretical quantity of benzene was taken. The substance crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless prisms melting at 48°, and was identified to be benzophenone.

Benzoylbenzoic Acid from Benzoylchloride and Benzoic Acid.

Benzoylchloride (7 g.), benzoic acid (6 g.) and chromium powder (5 g.) were heated together at 160° for about six hours, *i.e.*, until the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased. The product was then treated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid and then distilled in steam to remove the excess of benzoic acid. The residue was filtered and extracted with dilute ammonium hydroxide. The ammoniacal extract on acidification gave a colourless precipitate which was crystallised from hot water in shining white plates, m.p. 94°, and was identified to be benzoylbenzoic acid.

Acetophenone from Acetylchloride and Benzene.

A mixture of benzene (15 g.), acetylchloride (20 g.) and chromium powder (6 g.) was heated on the water-bath under reflux for about three hours. The mixture was then poured into crushed ice and the supernatant layer of benzene separated. This was washed with dilute sodium hydroxide and water, dried and then distilled. The portion distilling between 180° and 200° was collected. Acetophenone came over as a colourless oil. The oxime melted at 59° and the phenylhydrazone at 105°.

Diethyl succinate from Ethyl chloracetate and Ethyl acetate.

Ethyl chloracetate (12.2 g.), ethyl acetate (8.8 g.), and powdered chromium (4 g.) were heated together under reflux for about 3 hours, at 120°-130°. The mixture was then filtered off from the unaltered chromium powder and fractionated at the ordinary pressure, the portion distilling between 200° and 215° being collected. This was redistilled and collected between 216° and 218°, and the distillate was identified to be diethyl succinate.

Succinic Acid from Chloracetic Acid and Acetic Acid.

Sodium chloracetate (11 g.), sodium acetate (8 g.) and chromium powder (4 g.) were heated together at 110°-120° for about nine hours. The reaction product was then treated with dilute hydrochloric acid and filtered off from the unreacted chromium powder. The aqueous liquid on extraction with ether gave a small quantity of a crystalline solid melting at 185°, which was identified to be succinic acid.

Phenylanthranilic Acid from o-Chlorobenzoic Acid and Aniline.

A mixture of o-chlorobenzoic acid (5 g.), aniline (20 g.) and chromium powder (4 g.) was heated under reflux on the sand-bath for about four hours. The dark coloured reaction product was poured into excess of dilute hydrochloric acid when a brown precipitate separated out. This was filtered off, washed with water and dilute acid and finally crystallised from alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal in fine colourless plates melting at 183°, and was identified to be phenylanthranilic acid. When heated with concentrated sulphuric acid and poured into water, the substance gave acridone as a yellow precipitate, which did not melt even at 300°.

Anthranilic Acid from o-Chlorobenzoic Acid and Ammonia.

A mixture of o-chlorobenzoic acid (2.5 g.) and chromium powder (4 g.) was heated in a tube at 100° and a current of dry ammonia passed over the mixture for about five hours. The product was then treated with dilute hydrochloric acid until the precipitate first formed completely redissolved. An excess of saturated sodium acetate was then added, when the anthranilic acid was precipitated in brown flocks which were crystallised from hot water with the addition of animal charcoal in almost colourless needles melting at 143°.

The details of unsuccessful attempts are omitted. Further work in this direction is in progress.